

Germany) were prepared following standard methods¹, and stock solutions ($7.5 \times 10^{-2} M$) of the ligands were prepared in freshly distilled ethanol. Standard acetate buffers were prepared from acetic acid and sodium acetate.

A Elico LI-120 pH-meter was used for pH measurements and a Unicam SP 600 spectrophotometer for absorbance values.

A 10 ml test solution was prepared by mixing $1.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ Fe^{III} solution (1 ml) with $7.5 \times 10^{-2} M$ ethanolic solution (3 ml) of the ligands and the acetate buffer (1 ml), and the volume made up with double-distilled water.

Procedures for determination of Fe^{III} :

With o-vanillinoxime : An excess of the reagent solution in ethanol was added to ferric ion solution. The pH was adjusted to 5.0 for the blue complex or 7.0 for the red complex. The total volume was then made up to 10 ml after adding sufficient ethanol to make it 30% in ethanol.

The blue as well as the red complex was extracted into distilled chloroform (10 ml) and shaken mechanically for ~ 10 min. The organic phase was then separated by centrifugation and the absorbance measured at 550 nm (for the blue complex) and 580 nm (for the red complex) against chloroform blank.

With o-vanillinsemicarbazone : To a known volume of solution of ferric ion was added excess of semicarbazone solution in ethanol. pH of the solution was adjusted in the range 5.0–6.0 and the solution made up to 10 ml keeping ethanol concentration at 30%. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 550 nm against the reagent blank.

With o-vanillinthiosemicarbazone : To a known volume of the ferric solution was added excess of thiosemicarbazone solution in ethanol. pH of the solution was adjusted to 5.8–7.0 and the volume made up to 10 ml keeping 30% in ethanol. The absorbance was measured at 590 nm against the reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Fe^{III} -3-methoxysalicylaldoxime system : The oxime gave a blue complex with Fe^{III} at low pH values (2.0–5.1, 30% ethanol). The blue colour discharged in ~ 20 min. It was found to be 1 : 2 complex by the Job's method of continuous variation at pH 5.0 (λ_{max} 550 nm, ϵ , $4 \times 10^3 m^2 mol^{-1}$ and sensitivity 4.5 ppm). A red complex stable for 12 h was obtained at higher pH-values (6.0 to 8.0, 30% ethanol) which exhibited λ_{max} 580 nm, ϵ $4.01 \times 10^3 m^2 mol^{-1}$ and sensitivity 1.5 ppm at pH 7. Both the blue and red complexes were totally extractable from their solutions in 30% ethanol by non-polar solvents like chloroform and carbon tetrachloride. In these solvents the blue complex was found to be stable for 4 h whereas the red complex was quite stable (24 h). Standard deviations from ten determinations for the blue and red complexes were 0.005 and 0.003, respectively.

Tolerance of some ions (ppm) for the red complex containing 1.5 ppm Fe^{III} were as follows : chloride (1000), bromide (1000), iodide (400), sulphate (600), thiosulphate (200), Zn^{II} (60), Pb^{II} (260), Cd^{II} (50), Ce^{III} (104) and Th^{IV} (100).

Fe^{III} -3-methoxysalicylaldehyde semicarbazone system : The semicarbazone gave with Fe^{III} a stable yellow 2 : 1 complex in the pH range 4.0–5.7 (30% ethanol). The yellow complex was not extractable in non-polar solvents. It exhibited λ_{max} at 550 nm with $\epsilon = 5360 m^2 mol^{-1}$ and sensitivity 3.75 ppm at pH 5. The value for the standard deviation from ten determinations for the complex was 0.004.

Traces of Cu^{II} , Co^{II} , Mn^{II} , Sb^{III} , Ti^{IV} , Sn^{IV} , citrate and oxalate interfered seriously in determination of 3.75 ppm Fe^{III} at pH 5. Small amounts of Sn^{IV} and Ti^{IV} were masked by fluoride ions and that of Sb^{V} by tartrate ions. The tolerance of some other ions (ppm) were as follows : phosphate (400), acetate (20), iodate (400), iodide (15), bromide (1000), Zn^{II} (800), Mg^{II} (200), Be^{III} (15), Zr^{IV} (25), Al^{III} (26), V^{V} (12), As^{III} (374), Ce^{III} (28), Cd^{II} (400) and Mo^{VI} (20).

Fe^{III} -3-methoxysalicylaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone system : The thiosemicarbazone gave with Fe^{III} a 1 : 2 stable yellowish green complex at pH 5.8–7.0 (30% ethanol). The complex was not extractable in non-polar solvents. The yellowish green complex exhibited λ_{max} at 590 nm with $\epsilon = 5060 m^2 mol^{-1}$ and sensitivity 3.95 ppm at pH 6.5. The value for the standard deviation from ten determinations were 0.003. Traces of iodate, Cu^{II} , Co^{II} , Cr^{III} and Ag^I interfered in determination of 3.95 ppm Fe^{III} at pH 6.5. The tolerance (ppm) for the other ions were as follows : bromide (1000), chloride (1500), iodide (500), fluoride (4), phosphate (4), oxalate (20), Ni^{II} (10), Pb^{II} (500), Zn^{II} (400), Cd^{II} (360), Sr^{III} (600), Mn^{II} (40), Sb^{III} (48), As^{III} (187), Th^{IV} (400) and Mo^{VI} (20).

Reference

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Quantitative Determination of Metronidazole Benzoate in Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms by Glc

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METRONIDAZOLE benzoate, i.e. 2-[2-methyl-5-nitro-imidazol-1-yl]ethylbenzoate, is an anti-amoebic drug and is used in oral suspension as an acceptable tasteless form to be administered to children. It has antiprotozoal and antibacterial

actions and is official in Indian pharmacopoeia¹. The present official method of analysis included in Indian pharmacopoeia is based on simple non-aqueous titration with perchloric acid. In literature few methods for the analysis of metronidazole benzoate have been described which include glc^{2,3} and tlc⁴. Gorogs *et al.*² reported the use of glc in the investigation of metronidazole benzoate from its suspension formulations on column packed with 3% OV 225 on Chromosorb W-HP, Gutierrez and Garzon³ reported studies on the stability of metronidazole benzoate by gc after separating the drug by tlc.

The present note describes a direct quantitative method for the determination of metronidazole benzoate in pharmaceutical dosage forms by gas chromatography using tinidazole as internal standard.

Experimental

An analytical gas chromatography (model Omega manufactured by Netel Chromatographs, a division of Universal Ferro and Allied Chemicals Ltd.) with a flame ionisation detector and Anamed-308 computing integrator was used. A stainless steel column (1 m × 3.2 mm) packed with 3% OV 17 on Chromosorb W-HP (100–120 mesh) was used. Temperature of the oven was set at 220° and that of the injection port and detector were set at 300°. The carrier N₂ gas flow rate was maintained at 45 ml min⁻¹.

Chloroform used was of G.R. grade.

Internal standard solution: Tinidazole (100%) was used as internal standard. A solution of tinidazole (1.2%, w/v) in chloroform was prepared as internal standard.

Working standard preparation: Metronidazole benzoate (99.97%; ~0.9 g) was accurately weighed and dissolved in chloroform in a calibrated measuring flask and the volume made up to 100 ml. An aliquot (2 ml) of the solution was pipetted into a 10 ml calibrated flask, followed by internal standard solution (4 ml) and diluted to the mark with chloroform.

Preparation of samples for glc analysis: Metronidazole benzoate pure drug (~0.9 g) was accurately weighed and the procedure as in working standard preparation was followed for preparing its solution.

In the case of metronidazole benzoate suspension, weight per ml of the suspension was determined and the sample equivalent to contain 0.9 g of metronidazole benzoate was pipetted in 250 ml separatory funnel. It was extracted with chloroform (4 × 20 ml), total chloroform extract was collected in 100 ml calibrated flask and diluted to the volume with chloroform. An aliquot (2 ml) of the solution was transferred to 10 ml calibrated flask followed by addition of internal standard solution (4 ml) and diluted to the volume with chloroform.

Glc analysis of metronidazole benzoate: Chromatogram (Fig. 1) using 0.7 microlitre aliquot of each of the working standard and working samples were taken. By comparing the peak area ratio of metronidazole benzoate in the samples and the standard, the amount of metronidazole benzoate per 5 ml of suspension was calculated as follows.

Fig. 1. Chromatogram of (I) tinidazole and (II) metronidazole benzoate.

$$\% \text{ Metronidazole benzoate} = F \times \frac{AT}{AS} \times \frac{WS}{WT} \times 100$$

$$\% \text{ Metronidazole benzoate in dosage form}$$

$$= F \times \frac{AT}{AS} \times \frac{WS}{WT} \times \frac{AW}{D} \times 100$$

where, F is the dilution factor, AT the peak area ratio of the sample relative to the internal standard, AS the peak area ratio of the standard relative to the internal standard, WS the weight of the standard taken, WT the weight or volume of the suspension taken, AW the average weight of the unit dosage

(average weight of 5 ml suspension) and *D* the labelled amount of the drug.

Linearity: The linearity of the plot (not shown) of the ratio of the peak area of metronidazole benzoate to that of the internal standard against the concentration of metronidazole benzoate showed that the method can be safely used at least upto 6 mg ml^{-1} concentration of the drug.

Recovery studies were undertaken to determine the accuracy of the method. Known amount of standard metronidazole benzoate were added to the fixed quantity of pre-analysed sample and were estimated by the proposed method. From the amount of metronidazole benzoate found, the percentage of recovery was calculated (Table 1).

TABLE 1—RECOVERY OF METRONIDAZOLE BENZOATE AT FOUR DIFFERENT LEVELS OF ADDITION ($n=7$)

Standard metronidazole benzoate added mg ml^{-1}	Mean \pm SD of amount recovered by proposed method mg ml^{-1}	Mean recovery \pm SD %
0.0	1.95 ± 0.01	—
1.8	3.69 ± 0.03	98.35 ± 0.73
2.7	4.69 ± 0.04	100.82 ± 0.71
3.6	5.54 ± 0.03	99.86 ± 0.46

Some commercial samples of metronidazole benzoate and its dosage form with single ingredient as well as in combination with other active ingredients were analysed by the proposed method and the results are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2—GLC ANALYSIS OF SOME COMMERCIAL SAMPLES OF METRONIDAZOLE BENZOATE

Sl. no.	Sample	Ingredients	Dose mg/5 ml	% Amount of label claim
1.	Suspension with single ingredient	Metronidazole benzoate	322.5	100.11
2.	Suspension with single ingredient	Metronidazole benzoate	322.5	105.32
3.	Suspension in combination	(i) Metronidazole benzoate	322.5	97.5
		(ii) Furazolidine	40.0	—
4.	Suspension in combination	(i) Metronidazole benzoate	120.95	103.22
		(ii) Furazolidine	25.0	—
		(iii) Pectin	50.0	—
		(iv) Light kaolin	1000.0	—

Discussion

We believe that the proposed assay method is the first gas chromatographic procedure developed for the quantitative estimation of metronidazole benzoate in pharmaceutical dosage forms. Previous methods^{2,3} by glc are on investigation and stability of the drug but not in pharmaceutical formulations of the drug in combination with other active ingredients. The results of the recovery experiments (Table 1) indicate that the method is accurate and reproducible. The advantage of the proposed method is that, it is not only direct but it also requires no separation of the drug from other active ingredients in the dosage form. Further, it does not require any derivatisation.

The proposed method was tested by assaying four suspension formulations out of which two were in combination with other active ingredients. Possibility of interfering peaks was checked by injecting all the active ingredients present in the suspension containing metronidazole benzoate, furazolidone, pectin and light kaolin individually one by one and found that none of the active syrup components co-eluted with the metronidazole benzoate or internal standard. The extraction method excludes all the inactive and few active components of the suspension and does not interfere in the assay of metronidazole benzoate as shown in the chromatogram.

The data (Table 2) indicate that the method gives accurate results for the various formulations since there is a good agreement with the label concentrations in all the cases. The proposed glc procedure is rapid, and one person can analyse 20–30 samples daily on an average.

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